

UNREALFIRE: A SYNTHETIC DATASET CREATION PIPELINE FOR ANNOTATED FIRE IMAGERY IN UNREAL ENGINE

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ABSTRACT

High-quality training data are essential for Deep Neural Network (DNN) training. In Natural Disaster Management (NDM) scenarios, annotated training data are needed to train DNN models, e.g., for wildfire detection/segmentation. However, image annotation in such scenarios is prone to annotation errors, mostly due to the unpredictable visual structure of the fire/smoke. To this end, photorealistic simulators hold substantial promise, since they allow the creation of synthetic wildfire images. Yet, existing assets depicting fires in simulator engines are typically inserted as particle objects. As a result, existing assets do not feature a set 3D mesh causing them to have no 2D projection, i.e., it is not trivial how to generate fire segmentation annotation maps. This paper presents a free, open-access¹ pipeline for creating diverse synthetic annotated wildfire image datasets. More specifically, we developed a novel particle segmentation camera for the AirSim plugin, which enables the generation of segmentation maps of objects made of particles. We also integrate Procedural Content Generation tools (PCG) to gather unlimited amounts of diverse, high-quality annotated training data. To evaluate our framework, we generated a sample fire dataset called AUTH-Unreal-Wildfire (AUW) for wildfire segmentation. In our experiments we use a state-of-the-art segmentation DNN, namely PID-Net, and compare the our synthetic wildfire images to different real image datasets, along with their potential to augment real wildfire datasets.

Index Terms— Drone/UAV, Synthetic Data Creation, Disaster Simulation, Wildfire Segmentation, Unreal Engine 5

1. INTRODUCTION

Deep neural networks (DNNs) are predominantly used for data analysis in Natural Disaster Management (NDM) events and scenarios. Notably, DNN models have been employed [1, 2] to process visual data captured from aerial sources in order to extract wildfire segmentation maps. DNN training for wildfire segmentation tasks requires access to high-quality, pixel-accurate segmented data. Existing methods have been trained on standardized, humanly annotated wildfire segmentation benchmarks.

Existing wildfire image region segmentation datasets, such as FLAME [3] or Corsican [4], constitute significant benchmarks

This work has received funding from the European Commission—European Union’s HORIZON EUROPE (HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions) under grant agreement 101093003 (TEMA). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union—European Commission. Neither the European Commission nor the European Union can be held responsible for them.

¹code: will be released upon paper acceptance

Fig. 1: Our proposed UnrealFire pipeline for the creation of the annotated synthetic images using the modified version of AirSim with our particle segmentation camera.

in nearly every wildfire image region segmentation or wildfire flame detection system utilizing DNN, for NDM purposes. While DNN models exhibit commendable accuracy when tested on these datasets, their generalization capacity is inherently limited by real-world factors, i.e., the environmental conditions and 3D terrain structure the above-mentioned datasets. Real wildfire image datasets will always be limited by the fact that, prescribed fires for data collection purposes, must be contained and not be situated near flammable materials, considerably restricting the variety of 3D scenery that can be captured, thus limiting their applicability in real-world conditions.

The most common ways for synthetic image creation are game engines (e.g. Unreal Engine, Unity) or generative machine learning models (e.g. GANs, Diffusion models). Although either of these methods can produce high-quality images, many of them can not produce accurate segmentation maps or any at all. Existing plugins for game engines like AirSim [5] or CARLA [6], come with segmentation map generation functionalities, however, even those are limited. With current methods it is not possible to project particle or transparent objects into the 2D annotation maps. This severely limits the use cases and types of synthetic images that can be created as most liquid, gas, or plasma objects need to be rendered as particle objects to capture their swiftly changing shapes.

In this context, our proposed method leverages the cutting-edge capabilities of Unreal Engine (UE) 5, an industry-leading platform in game creation and cinema, for creating photorealistic simulations of natural disasters, e.g. wildfire. Various 3D terrain models can be incorporated in UE 5, such as 3D forested regions or towns. To further enhance the fidelity of our simulations, we have employed

the AirSim [5] plugin of UE 5. It enables the emulation of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) perspective for image or video data gathering from the simulated environments. Our main contribution which enables the UnrealFire pipeline to generate annotated images is the creation of the particle segmentation camera, by modifying the source code of AirSim. This new camera can generate the 2D projections of particles in the 3D Unreal Engine simulation. Moreover, using the Procedural Content Generation tools (PCG) that Unreal Engine 5 offers, we are able to create extensive and rich simulated UAV image data with high variability just by adjusting tunable PCG hyperparameter without changing the simulated environments.

2. RELATED WORK

Several notable efforts have been undertaken to address the dearth of publicly available semantic wildfire image segmentation datasets, or natural disaster datasets, in general. Among these, FLAME [3], FLAME2 [7], and Corsican Fire Database [4] datasets have been extensively used due to their comprehensive coverage of wildfire incidents. These datasets are invaluable for researchers and practitioners seeking to develop robust and reliable DNN data analysis.

Synthetic NDM data offer a compelling alternative to address the aforementioned limitations [8]. Using the advanced Unreal Engine 5, we can construct an efficient and scalable pipeline for synthetic image creation [9]. Previous work [10] highlight the importance of synthetic datasets for augmenting real DNN training datasets and increasing DNN prediction accuracy [11].

In recent years, latent diffusion models have also become increasingly popular for their ability to synthesize high-quality images using different modalities as input, e.g. text, depth images, edge maps, poses images, their combination, etc [12, 13]. Synthetic images that were generated with diffusion models have indeed been used for DNN training to increase object detection and semantic image segmentation [14, 15, 16, 17].

Diffusion models can generate large amounts of synthetic images can be generated by simple text prompts. However, these images are not always pre-annotated, and in some cases, their segmentation masks may not be as precise as a manually annotated one or a game engine segmented mask. In cases when we want to create synthetic wildfire images based on a real forest image, the diffusion model synthesized images may not be as close to real-world images the as simulated ones with a 3D forest terrain model. This ability to set precise image acquisition conditions (e.g., environmental, vegetate ones) justifies synthetic image creation of data with game engines and 3D terrain modeling software, especially using well-defined and efficient pipelines.

The Simulator we choose is Unreal Engine version 5.2.1. It is compatible with AirSim and provides the excellent photorealism of using Ray Tracing on 3D scenes with 3D mesh objects. The plethora of publicly available 3D models ensures diversity in the datasets, providing the ability to model our simulation after varying real-world scenery. World Machine, Autodesk Maya, Blender can be used to create any type of 3D mesh model can be created that is not already available. Our software of choice regarding terrain is World Machine, standing out for its ease of use, and Blender for the 3D meshes as it offers precise and efficient modeling. Actors are the main simulation components that determine the object behavior in the scene. Unreal Engine has limitless possibilities to fit the simulation to our specific needs. Another component, as important as the actors, is the 3D meshes we are going to use for our objects. The Procedural Content Generation (PCG) tool, which is going to be

explained thoroughly later, enables the randomization of simulation parameters such as light condition, mesh sizes and orientation, etc.

AirSim is an autonomous virtual vehicle plugin in Unreal Engine that comes with a refined vehicle physics model. The vehicle is equipped with a set of different virtual cameras (e.g. depth, LiDAR, event camera, etc) that can easily be used for data gathering. AirSim vehicles can be cars or drones. A user-friendly Python API can effectively be used for vehicle mission planning, images acquisition, or even to change simulation settings. For visual data (image or video) acquisition, the UAV can simply fly around the area of interest (ROI) at a set speed, while capturing images from various view angles and locations, as the vehicle motion simulation evolves.

3. METHODOLOGY

Simulation creation: World Machine is used to model a high-detail 3D terrain model depicting forested hills and valleys using manual modeling and some additive noise for high-frequency 3D terrain variations. World Machine offers a variety of tools to model any type of 3D terrain with seamless export to Unreal Engine. This can be helpful for either adding 3D terrain variety or for creating specific 3D terrain landmarks and structures modeled after a physical location. The main actors used in this scene are trees, bushes, and other vegetation or burnable objects. These actors, alongside static objects, e.g., rocks, can be manually placed in the scene or are spawned in the scene by the PCG tool using on a number of parameters that are examined in the corresponding subsection. The main simulation focus is the spread of a wildfire between these objects. The wildfire simulation should be computationally light without sacrificing any temporal resolution. To this end, we did not incorporate any advanced wildfire spread algorithm [18, 19], as the benefits did not outweigh the computational cost for this specific use case. Each actor has a sphere with a predefined radius. At the start of each simulation, actors store the distance from each other neighbor actor if their spheres overlap. An actor's condition is determined by the condition of its neighbors. Before the simulation starts, one or more 'starting' actors can be chosen to gradually ignite or be already burning. Then, their fire can spread to their neighbors, at a rate based on the distance between them. Each actor has a set of parameters that control virtual fire spread and simulation conditions as shown in Table 1.

By tuning these parameters, different wildfire behaviors can emerge for catering different simulations needs. In the process of object burning, object mesh will gradually change, starting from the original mesh to a fully burned one, while spawning ash and burned logs around a burning tree (actor). Finally, the fire will continue to grow until it can not spread anymore, having either burned the entire 3D scene or only one region, in case its burning actors do not have any neighbors to spread fire to them. There is a single C++ base class that contains the logical for the behaviors described above, whose children are specific actors each having different parameters.

Each flammable actor can have multiple fire or smoke assets. Many publicly available fire assets can be found that are realistic enough for the simulation needs. However, all of these assets are particle assets and not mesh assets, leading to them not registering in the generated 2D segmentation maps. We developed the particle segmentation camera to overcome this problem and enable the generation annotated wildfire images.

Particle segmentation camera: One of the most helpful AirSim features is semantic segmentation capabilities via a virtual camera that is pre-loaded in the plugin. This camera outputs a segmentation mask of the RGB image from the main camera, coloring each object using a palette of 256 colors. These masks are pixel-accurate as each

Table 1: Parameters of actor simulating a burnable object

Parameter	Type	Usage
Fires	TArray <AActor*>	Array containing the fire actor particle assets
FiresPosition	TArray <FVector>	Array containing the position of the fires
Smokes	TArray <AActor*>	Array containing the smoke actor particle assets
SmokesPosition	TArray <FVector>	Array containing the position of the smoke actors
DeadLog	UStaticMesh*	Mesh for fallen logs
Ash	UMaterialInstance*	Mesh for ashes
RiseSpeed	float	Speed the fire/smoke rises
DecaySpeed	float	Speed the fire/smoke decays
FireMaxScale	float	Maximum scale of the fire
FireLiveTime	int	Time the fire stays at its maximum scale
StartFireTemp	int	Threshold to start the fires/smokes
SmokeStartAt	int	Time lag for the smoke to start
SphereRadius	float	Sphere radius for finding neighboring actors

3D object is projected on the 2D image plane to form one 2D region in the segmentation map. However, one of the biggest difficulties we encountered was getting the fire segmentation mask. Fire objects are not registered in the default segmentation camera of AirSim as it does not support the 2D projection of transparent objects without a set 3D mesh. To this end, we created a particle segmentation AirSim camera. This process involved writing code for the plugin, as well as, creating a new custom Post Process Material to get the semantic segmentation map of fire particles. Post Process Materials are used to create visual screen effects, by manipulating various phases of the rendering buffer, also referred to as G-Buffer. AirSim can add secondary cameras to the screen with custom Post Process Materials to achieve different effects, e.g., depth camera, segmentation, etc. The Post Process Material we created loads the captured image from the G-Buffer at a stage where transparent objects, such as fire, were not rendered, as well as the final image, visualizing the whole scene. Subtracting the first from the latter results in an image where the only colored pixels are those from transparent objects, in this case, fire particles. Adding this Post Process Material to a new AirSim camera positioned at the exact point where the RGB camera enables us to generate the binary segmentation map, containing pixels where there is fire and pixels where there is not, colored accordingly. Using this technique, custom cameras can be made, e.g. a thermal camera can be made or something more specific, like Skydio’s firefighting camera to train DNNs on specific types of images.

Scalability and benchmarking : Data diversity is imperative for the robust and effective training of the DNNs for NDM tasks. The ability to diversify disaster simulations is one of the key factors supported by synthetic data. Another important property of UnrealFire pipeline is the delivery of large DNN training and testing datasets. The Procedural Content Generation (PCG) tools that come bundled with UE 5 into the pipeline renders the creation of different wildfire simulations effortless and requires minimal time consumption. The main component of the PCG framework is PCG graphs that store content generation parameters and logic. It is used to spawn actors with different meshes, representing different types of vegetation or objects like rocks, buildings, etc. For each actor, there are different parameters, such as spawn density, random scaling, random rotations, and actor distances. These parameters can be set manually or can be randomly changed, thus efficiently creating different scenery types. Moreover, vegetation, terrain, lighting, structure, type swapping on the fly, enables rich and varying data collection that is almost impossible to obtain when relying on real-world settings. Another

AirSim plugin advantage is the option to support various weather conditions. Using Python AirSim API, can digitally process the captured images to add different weather effects, such as rain, snow, dust, fog, etc., both in the RGB image and in the annotated image segmentation mask.

AirSim can support a very high image capture rate, depending on the computational power of the rendering computer. There are options that enhance computing speed, e.g., not rendering anything on the screen or by adjusting the simulation clock. Furthermore, the virtual drone can spend more time over each 3D region by adjusting its flying velocity. Our testing system consists of an Intel i7-9700 CPU, 32 GB of RAM, and a Nvidia GTX 1080 Ti GPU. Packaging UE 5 project takes about 20-30 minutes. Its simulation with 1500 to 2000 actors runs at an average of 75 fps without significant video frame dropping. Capturing an area with many actors from different angles can generate more than 500 Mb of data corresponding to around 400, 600 x 800 pixel images. A wildfire scenario on a large 3D scene, evolving till its natural end when all its regions are burnt, can result in several GB of annotated images.

4. AUW DATASET

Finally, we have employed the proposed framework in order to generate a synthetic dataset named AUTH-Unreal-Wildfires, hereafter referred to as AUW. Through the proposed UnrealFire pipeline can be used to extract any large number of annotated images, to be on par with the real datasets, we have used it to create 1700 RGB image - segmentation mask pairs, split into train and validation sets. These images are captured from 6 different simulations featuring distinct environmental, geological, and illumination conditions, resulting in a wide variety of training data as illustrated in Fig.2. A visual comparison between AUW and real image datasets is shown in Fig 3.

Pre-processing: We tested different pre-processing setups for the AirSim image segmentation masks. While the AirSim masks are pixel-accurate, this is not the case for real datasets. The Unreal Engine 5 particles model may leave some small holes in the 3D fire, translating to small holes in the 2D segmentation mask. We used segmentation map dilation [20] on the masks for the fire regions with different dilation kernels and found that a dilation kernel of size (9, 9) works the best. However, the need for dilation and the kernel size, depend on other conditions, e.g., the texture of the fire.

Comparison with other datasets: The FLAME dataset [3] consists of 2003 RGB video frames at a resolution of 3480 X 2160 pixels

Fig. 2: Sample RGB image and segmentation mask pairs from our synthetic A UW dataset in various environments and conditions

Fig. 3: Comparison of real images from FLAME and Corsican (left side) and synthetic images from A UW dataset (right side).

that come together with their segmentation masks. It comprises of continuous video frames depicting a single forest scene covered in snow with some small fires. The Corsican Fire Database [4] is a collection of annotated fire images and videos at various resolutions, shot with various parameters, e.g., camera models, exposure time or lens sensitivity. The dataset has 500 and 100 images depicting wild-fires in the visible spectrum and in both the visible and infrared spectrum respectively. It also contains 5 sets of video frames, also both in the visible and infrared spectrum. Both datasets are frequently used in scientific studies [14]. However, both have limitations regarding their ability to generalize with respect to DNN training. The high-resolution images in the FLAME dataset, particularly the smaller fires which only make up 0.58% of the total pixels from the dataset, lose significant details when subsampled for DNN training, resulting in poor DNN segmentation accuracy. Some Corsican images have a rather low resolution and image clarity, affecting the ability of the segmentation network to generalize, as is shown later. The percent of pixels that belong to the fire class are 17.09%, which is significantly different than FLAME. Moreover, in 4, we can see that the probability of the fire class is more equally distributed in A UW rather than either FLAME or Corsican. For the FLAME training set we took the first 1501 frames and the rest 502 for test. For Corsican, all video frames along with 320 images was the training and 280 the test set. The training and test dataset sizes of the above-mentioned datasets are summarized in 2

Fig. 4: Probability heatmaps of fire class in each dataset.

5. DATASET BENCHMARKING IN DNN-BASED FIRE SEGMENTATION

Segmentation Network and Hyperparameters: The PIDNet segmentation DNN was chosen for our experiments [21]. PIDNet has three variants: PIDNet small, PIDNet medium, and PIDNet large. The variants have different model sizes, offering the ability to choose the desired trade-off between speed and accuracy. PIDNet medium was used in our testing, as it has real-time performance (over 100 fps) for our 600 x 800 pixel image resolution. We changed the default learning rate to $\alpha = 0.0055$ and the weights balance to around 0.99 and 0.01, depending on the datasets used, keeping every other parameter to the default PIDNet medium values. Finally, a method was implemented for augmenting the DNN training dataset by randomly changing image saturation and contrast.

Evaluation of A UW: In our first set of experiments, we train the PIDNet with A UW data, while at times augmenting with images from the Corsican dataset at various percentages (1%, 2%, 5%, 10%, 25%, 50%, 75%). Training was performed over 120 epochs. The PIDNet medium model with the best test accuracy was retained. Testing was performed on the Corsican test set and the results are illustrated in Table 3. When using only A UW synthetic images for training, the testing mIoU drops around 28% from the mIoU achieved by training on the Corsican dataset. When the percentage of real images in the training set is increased, the mIoU gets progressively better. Adding only 1% of Corsican images (11 images) to the A UW training set, the mIoU on the Corsican test set increases to 86%, now showing only a 5% drop. When the training set consists of A UW synthetic images and more than 10% of Corsican images, the mIoU and Fire IoU are better than the benchmark Corsican. Using both the A UW and Corsican training sets results in 2% increase in test accuracy vs the benchmark one. These results illustrate how a combination of mostly synthetic and a few real images can effectively replace large real images annotated datasets, while also adding more variety to the training set, resulting in higher test accuracy and generalization of wildfires.

For our second experiment, we tried the cross-dataset accuracy between FLAME, Corsican, and A UW, presented in Table 4. The Corsican dataset training set performs worse, when testing with the FLAME test set than the A UW training set. The dataset domains differ greatly. Images of the FLAME dataset depict small fires in a snow-covered environment with high resolution, while Corsican images contain large fires with different saturation and contrast. Thus, PIDNet, trained the with Corsican images, achieves only a 26.63%

Table 2: FLAME, Corsican, and A UW training and test datasets.

Dataset	Training images	Testing images	% of fire class pixels
FLAME	1501	502	0.58%
Corsican	842	280	17.09%
A UW	1500	200	2.5%

Table 3: Results on the test set of Corsican. A UW represents our synthetic training dataset. A UW + X% represents training with our synthetic training set combined with images from the Corsican training set. 75% represents the whole Corsican training set.

Training Dataset	Fire IoU	mIoU
Corsican	86.95	91.60
A UW	45.07	65.86
A UW + 1%	78.17	86.06
A UW + 2%	81.33	87.99
A UW + 5%	83.80	89.49
A UW + 10%	87.52	91.98
A UW + 25%	87.22	91.82
A UW + 50%	87.80	92.14
A UW + 75%	89.35	93.18

Table 4: Results on cross-dataset validation accuracy. + styling represents that the validation set was styled according to the training set.

Training Dataset	FLAME Validation		Corsican Validation	
	Fire IoU	mIoU	Fire IoU	mIoU
FLAME	83.40	91.66	58.05	69.38
Corsican	26.63	62.88	91.60	86.95
A UW	46.81	73.27	45.07	65.86
FLAME + styling	-	-	43.63	65.03
Corsican + styling	11.34	55.45	-	-
A UW + styling	50.82	75.27	63.79	77.01

Fire IoU when tested on the FLAME. When PIDNet is trained on A UW, it has almost double (46.81%) Fire IoU when tested on FLAME test set. This performance increase can be explained as follows. The high variety of synthetic images leads to the distribution in A UW being closer visually and structurally to FLAME.

In our third experiment, we used StyleID [22] to perform a style transfer between the synthetic and real images. StyleID works by taking a single image as reference and applies its style to the selected content images. StyleID was used with its default parameters, meaning the styled images in the experiments have a resolution of 512 X 512 pixels. For each experiment the test images were restyled according to the training dataset images. A UW was only for training while FLAME and Corsican were used for both training and testing. We tested different images for styling and used the one that resulted in the best test accuracy. The comparison results are illustrated in Table 4. Style transferring between the 2 real datasets did not improve the cross-dataset accuracy. Specifically, the effect of styling either the Corsican or FLAME test set, when training the PIDNet on the other, was a decrease in mIoU and fire IoU in both cases. This is a result of the highly different distributions in the images of the datasets, the effect styling distorts the images rather than improving their similarities. However, styling either real dataset with an image from A UW, increased the achieved mIoU. The archived mIoU with the styled FLAME test set increased 4%, surpassing even more the best mIoU that PIDNet trained on Corsican could achieve when tested on FLAME. In the case of the stylized Corsican test set, there is a 18% increase in fire IoU, surpassing the results of training with FLAME. The ability of our synthetic dataset to improve through styling stems from the more general nature of the images, as it includes better-structured wildfires without any highly specific effects (e.g., saturation, focal length, etc.) and is able to adapt better to other domains.

6. DISCUSSION

The results of the experiments reveal several insights into using synthetic datasets in DNN training for wildfire scenarios. Synthetic images alone cannot fully replace real images, highlighting the gap between synthetic and real image domains. Although valuable, neither FLAME nor Corsican datasets can be used to produce DNN models that can effectively generalize concerning each dataset’s validation sets. The structure of the FLAME dataset (e.g., small fires, snow environment, short drone flight time, and lack of diverse viewing angles) proves too specific for Corsican. Conversely, the images from the Corsican dataset (large fires, low resolution, lack of viewing angles, high saturation, etc.) cannot be used in DNN training to accurately segment FLAME. In a real NDM situation with specific environmental conditions, DNN’s predictions, whether trained with FLAME or Corsican, may not be sufficiently accurate.

On the other hand, A UW showcases various wildfire sizes, backgrounds, viewing angles, camera settings, and environmental conditions. In such cases, the significance of effortlessly generated synthetic images that better reflect disaster conditions than existing real images could facilitate more timely and cost-effective NDM responses. The results from the style transfer experiments further demonstrate the inability of real datasets to generalize as effectively as synthetic data. Style transferring between A UW and real datasets improved validation mIoU, lending credibility to the assertion that synthetic images struggle to perform like real ones due to visual differences. Reducing these visual differences through styling proves that our synthetic dataset can be utilized in general NDM systems for wildfire segmentation, as the images offer a greater diversity of scenery and improved generalization potential compared to existing real wildfire datasets. A UW can also serve as a baseline for wildfire segmentation tasks, featuring a more generalized depiction of a wildfire disaster.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the creation of synthetic datasets for NDM scenarios through our proposed UnrealFire pipeline, leveraging the advanced capabilities of Unreal Engine 5, AirSim, and utilizing our new particle segmentation camera represents a significant step forward in addressing the critical challenge of data scarcity in NDM DNN training, namely wildfire segmentation. The open-access modifications of AirSim, namely the particle segmentation camera, along with the UE 5 code provide a new way for researchers to create conditioned synthetic images from game engines for a plethora of machine learning applications. As proven by our experiments, the synthetic images created using our UnrealFire pipeline promise to bridge the gap left by real data, where they might fail because of the specific geographical or environmental conditions of the disaster. When used alongside real data, synthetic datasets can help the generalization of DNN training, improving the confidence of the predictions and leading to more effective NDM strategies.

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